

**GAIA GIORGI, VITTORIA MACARIO BAN,
ALESSIA RICCUMENI**

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NEW ORLEANS, LA

Annual report

CITY OF NEW ORLEANS

THE CITY OF NEW ORLEANS

New Orleans, is not just a place; it's a shared experience, a tapestry of diverse cultures, and a testament to the human spirit. The resilience that courses through the streets, the music that fills the air, and the love that binds the citizen together is what makes New Orleans truly special. This city has faced its share of challenges, but it always emerged stronger, more united, and more vibrant.

The city is committed to building a New Orleans that is safer, more equitable, and more sustainable. They'll continue to work towards improved public services, better educational opportunities, and a cleaner, greener city. They understand the importance of public safety, strong neighborhoods, and economic growth.

This report aims at providing an overview of the financial, social and cultural situation of New Orleans. The data conforms to generally accepted accounting principles. More detailed financial information can be found in the City's Comprehensive Annual Financial Report on the City's website at <https://nola.gov/next/home/>

THE MAYOR LATOYA CANTRELL

ABOUT OUR CITY

New Orleans, located on the Mississippi River, represents Louisiana's primary city and the busiest northern port on the Gulf of Mexico since the early 1700s.

The city of New Orleans has its origins in 1718 when it was founded by the French governor with the name of Nouvelle-Orléans. New Orleans has intrinsic Carnival traditions influenced by French and Spanish Catholicism, African and Native American customs.

During the 19th century, New Orleans became one of the wealthiest and third-largest cities in the United States, with a significant port for exporting goods to international destinations.

During the 20th century, despite challenges such as hurricanes and floods, New Orleans continued to grow and witnessed the birth of jazz.

After World War II, despite some poverty and social issues, New Orleans gained the status as a popular tourist destination, known for its unique Creole culture and events like Mardi Gras.

Our city's resilience was put to the test in 2005, when Hurricane Katrina hit. New Orleans had been evacuated, but the flooding affected 80 percent of the area claiming many lives and leaving thousands in severe conditions. Despite this, New Orleans showed us a very strong ability to recover from this kind of disaster, also thanks to additional help from outside.

The following report aims at providing our beloved citizens with a view of their city's financial, economic, social and demographic information with a specific focus on the financial report of year 2022.

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**City's
area**

350 square miles

Population

The table shows the changes in the population trends over time . In 2022 the population of the city of New Orleans was of 369,749 with a decrease of 3,7 % compared to 2020.

**Average
income**

73,344 U.S. dollars

**Average
educational level**

37% of New Orleans residents have a high school diploma or less, compared to 49% of all Louisiana and 39% of all U.S. residents, respectively.

SOME DATA

SOME DATA

Gender , age and ethnicity distribution

People under 5 years: 5,7%
People under 18 years: 20%
People over than 65 years: 15,2 %

The population of our city is composed by women for the 52,5 % and the 47,5 % is represented by men.

Sectors of trade and type of businesses

- Oil and Gas and related activities
- Tourism
- Port and ship/boat building
- Aerospace manufacturing

PUBLIC ADMINISTRATION

In New Orleans, public administration encompasses various groups, departments, and agencies that work together to deliver services to the city's residents and manage its operations

City
Government
City
Departments
Public Safety
Public
Transportation
Education

Housing and Urban
Development
Health and Social
Services
Environmental
Services
Cultural Services
Tourism and
Visitor Services

CITY GOVERNMENT

The city government of New Orleans, Louisiana, operates as a mayor-council system. Here is an overview of its structure:

- **Mayor:** The Mayor of New Orleans is the city's chief executive officer. The Mayor of New Orleans was LaToya Cantrell. The mayor is responsible for the overall administration of city government, setting policies, and representing the city at various levels.
- **City Council:** The New Orleans City Council is the legislative body of the city. It is composed of five district councilmembers and two at-large councilmembers, each representing specific geographic areas of the city. The City Council is responsible for passing ordinances, approving the city's budget, and overseeing the operation of city agencies. The City Council plays a crucial role in the governance and policy-making for New Orleans.
- **City Departments and Agencies:** New Orleans has a range of city departments and agencies that manage various aspects of city operations. These departments handle services related to public works, public safety, sanitation, transportation, health, housing, education, and more.
- **Judicial Branch:** The judicial branch of New Orleans includes the Municipal Court and Civil District Court. These courts handle various legal matters, including traffic violations, small claims, and civil cases.
- **Community Engagement:** New Orleans actively engages with the community through public meetings, town halls, and neighborhood associations. These community engagement efforts provide residents with opportunities to voice their concerns and provide input on city policies and initiatives.
- **Elections:** New Orleans holds municipal elections to select the Mayor, City Council members, and other city officials. The Registrar of Voters and the Orleans Parish Board of Supervisors of Elections oversee the election process.

CHIEF ADMINISTRATIVE OFFICE ORGANIZATIONAL CHART

Source: <https://nola.gov/chief-administrative-office/>

PUBLIC ADMINISTRATION

- **City Departments:**

- **Department of Public Works:** Responsible for managing infrastructure, streets, and sanitation services.
- **Department of Finance:** Manages the city's finances, budget, and taxation.
- **Department of Parks and Parkways:** Maintains and develops city parks and green spaces.
- **Department of Safety and Permits:** Oversees permitting, code enforcement, and building inspections.
- **Department of Health:** Manages public health services and sanitation.
- **Department of Property Management:** Manages city-owned properties.
- **Department of Sanitation:** Responsible for waste management and recycling services.
- **Department of Human Services:** Provides social services and assistance programs.

- **Public Safety:**

- **New Orleans Police Department (NOPD):** Enforces laws, maintains public safety, and responds to emergencies.
- **New Orleans Fire Department:** Provides fire suppression, emergency medical services, and disaster response.
- **Emergency Medical Services (EMS):** Offers emergency medical services.

- **Public Transportation:**

- **Regional Transit Authority (RTA):** Manages public transportation, including buses and streetcars

- **Education:**

- **New Orleans Public Schools:** Oversees the public education system in the city.
- **New Orleans Public Library:** Provides library services and resources to the community.

- **Housing and Urban Development:**

- **New Orleans Department of Housing and Community Development:** Manages housing and community development programs.

- **Health and Social Services:**

- **Louisiana Department of Health:** Provides public health services.
- **Louisiana Department of Children and Family Services:** Manages child welfare and family support programs.

- **Environmental Services:**

- **Sewerage and Water Board of New Orleans (SWBNO):** Manages water, sewage, and drainage services.
- **Office of Resilience and Sustainability:** Focuses on environmental and climate resilience initiatives.

- **Cultural Services:**

- **Arts Council New Orleans:** Promotes arts and culture in the city.

- **Tourism and Visitor Services:**

- **New Orleans Tourism Marketing Corporation:** Promotes tourism and cultural experiences in the city.

These groups and departments are responsible for delivering a wide range of public services, including infrastructure management, public safety, public health, education, and cultural promotion. The composition and specific services provided by each group may evolve over time as the city's needs change and new initiatives are introduced.

EMPLOYEES

BY GENDER

City of New Orleans
Employees Who
Are Women
50%

City of New Orleans
Executives Who
Are Women
62%

BY AGE

CITY COUNCIL DISTRICTS

New Orleans is divided into five City Council districts and each of them is represented by a council member who is responsible for representing the interests of the residents of their area.

Source: New Orleans City Council

DISTRICT A. JOSEPH I. GIARRUSSO III
DISTRICT B. LESLI HARRIS
DISTRICT C. FREDDIE KING III
DISTRICT D. EUGENE J. GREEN
DISTRICT E. OLIVER THOMAS

MAJOR POLICIES

New Orleans remains on the frontlines of climate change.

Key accomplishments include:

- **Office of Resilience and Sustainability (ORS)** released updated Climate Action Plan highlighting the initiatives in place to tackle the climate crisis and outlining ambitious goals to reduce our greenhouse gas emissions and achieve Net Zero, or carbon neutrality, by 2050
- Mayor's Office of Transportation partnered with Entergy New Orleans to construct 30 electric vehicle (EV) charging stations in 25 locations as part of the Climate Action for a Resilient New Orleans strategy

Sustainability and environmental initiatives are crucial for any city, and New Orleans is no exception. The city has faced significant environmental challenges, particularly concerning hurricane protection, flood control, and coastal erosion. In response to these challenges, New Orleans has implemented various sustainability and environmental initiatives to protect its natural resources and promote a more sustainable future. Some of these initiatives include:

- **Resilience Planning:** New Orleans has developed comprehensive resilience plans, such as the Greater New Orleans Urban Water Plan and the Resilient New Orleans strategy. These plans focus on flood protection, water management, and climate adaptation.
- **Flood Protection and Stormwater Management:** The city has invested in upgrading and maintaining the drainage and pumping systems to mitigate flooding.
- **Coastal Restoration:** The CPRA and other agencies work on restoring Louisiana's coastal ecosystems to protect the city from hurricanes and coastal erosion.
- **Green Infrastructure:** New Orleans promotes green infrastructure, such as permeable pavement, rain gardens, and green roofs, to manage stormwater and reduce flooding.
- **Energy Efficiency:** The city has implemented energy efficiency programs in public buildings and encourages sustainable construction and development practices.
- **Public Transportation:** The Regional Transit Authority (RTA) has improved public transportation, which can reduce the city's carbon footprint and alleviate traffic congestion.
- **Sustainable Tourism:** The city promotes eco-friendly and sustainable tourism practices to preserve natural resources and protect the environment.
- **Environmental Education and Awareness:** Various organizations and initiatives, work to educate residents and visitors about environmental issues and solutions.

New Orleans is continually working to balance the need for sustainability and environmental protection with the challenges posed by its unique geographic and environmental context. These initiatives reflect a commitment to creating a more resilient and eco-friendly city that can better withstand future environmental challenges.

MAJOR POLICIES

Community engagement in New Orleans is an essential aspect of the city's governance and development. The city has a history of strong community involvement, particularly in the wake of significant events such as Hurricane Katrina. Here are some key elements of community engagement in New Orleans:

- **Neighborhood Associations:** New Orleans has a network of neighborhood associations that play a vital role in representing the interests of residents. These associations often work with the city government on issues such as public safety, infrastructure, and community development.
- **Public Meetings:** The city hosts various public meetings and town hall sessions where residents can voice their concerns, provide input on proposed policies, and engage in discussions with city officials.
- **City Council Engagement:** The New Orleans City Council offers opportunities for public comment on various matters, including proposed legislation and budgetary issues. Residents can participate in council meetings to express their views.

- **Community Development Block Grants (CDBG):** The city receives federal CDBG funds that are allocated to community development projects based on community input. Residents can have a say in how these funds are used in their neighborhoods.
- **Partnerships and Collaborations:** The city often collaborates with community organizations and nonprofits to address various issues, including affordable housing, education, and public health.
- **Youth Engagement:** Initiatives are in place to engage and empower the city's youth through youth councils and leadership programs.
- **Online and Social Media Engagement:** New Orleans uses digital channels to engage residents, gather input, and provide updates on city initiatives.
- **Disaster Preparedness:** Given the city's vulnerability to natural disasters, community engagement is vital in disaster preparedness and recovery. Organizations like Evacuteer.org and the Office of Homeland Security and Emergency Preparedness work to engage residents in disaster planning.
- **Cultural and Arts Engagement:** New Orleans' vibrant cultural and arts scene often includes community involvement in cultural preservation, arts festivals, and related activities.
- **Community Policing:** The New Orleans Police Department fosters community engagement through community policing programs to build trust and partnerships between law enforcement and residents.
- **Health and Social Services Engagement:** Various organizations and agencies work with communities to address public health issues, social services, and wellness initiatives.

Community engagement is a key component of New Orleans' efforts to address the needs and concerns of its diverse population. It plays a significant role in shaping the city's policies, services, and development plans to ensure they are aligned with the interests and well-being of its residents.

MAJOR POLICIES

Cultural and educational initiatives play a significant role in the rich and diverse fabric of New Orleans. These initiatives aim to celebrate and preserve the city's unique culture, history, and heritage, as well as provide educational opportunities for its residents. While I don't have access to specific initiatives for the year 2022, here are some general examples of the types of cultural and educational initiatives that are typically found in New Orleans:

Cultural Initiatives:

- **Festivals:** New Orleans is famous for its festivals, including Mardi Gras, the New Orleans Jazz & Heritage Festival, and French Quarter Festival. These events celebrate the city's music, art, cuisine, and culture.
- **Historical Preservation:** Initiatives to preserve and protect the city's rich historical and cultural heritage, including historic building preservation, guided historical tours, and cultural heritage programs.
- **Public Art:** Support for public art installations, murals, and sculptures that enhance the city's visual appeal and cultural identity.
- **Cultural Exchange:** Programs that promote cultural exchange and understanding, often involving partnerships with international cities and cultural organizations.
- **Music Education:** Initiatives to provide music education opportunities to residents, particularly in the areas of jazz and brass band traditions.

Educational Initiatives:

- **Public Education:** Efforts to improve the quality of public education in the city, including curriculum development, teacher training, and programs for at-risk students.
- **Higher Education:** Support for local colleges and universities, including Tulane University, the University of New Orleans, and others, which play a crucial role in the city's educational landscape.
- **STEM and STEAM Programs:** Initiatives to promote science, technology, engineering, arts, and mathematics education, including after-school programs and STEM/STEAM events.
- **Literacy Programs:** Promoting literacy and reading among children and adults through library programs, book festivals, and literacy events.
- **Cultural Education:** Programs that educate students and the public about the city's rich cultural history, including music, cuisine, and traditions.
- **Youth Mentorship and Career Development:** Initiatives to provide mentorship and career development opportunities for young people, helping them explore various career paths.
- **Online and Remote Learning:** Expanding online and remote learning opportunities, particularly in response to challenges posed by the COVID-19 pandemic.
- **Community Centers:** Support for community centers and programs that provide educational and enrichment opportunities for residents, especially in underserved neighborhoods.

MAJOR POLICIES

New Orleans provides a range of public services to its residents and visitors. These services are essential for the functioning and well-being of the city. Here are some of the key public services in New Orleans:

- **Emergency Services:**
 - New Orleans Police Department (NOPD): Responsible for law enforcement and ensuring public safety.
 - New Orleans Fire Department: Provides fire suppression, emergency medical services, and disaster response.
 - Emergency Medical Services (EMS): Offers medical services in emergency situations.
- **Public Transportation:**
 - Regional Transit Authority (RTA): Manages buses and streetcars for public transportation in the city.
 - Louis Armstrong New Orleans International Airport: Provides air transportation services.
- **Healthcare:**
 - Hospitals: The city has several hospitals and healthcare facilities to meet medical needs.

- **Social Services:**
 - Department of Health and Human Services: Offers various social and public assistance programs.
 - Department of Children and Family Services: Provides services related to child welfare and family support.
- **Public Utilities:**
 - Sewerage and Water Board of New Orleans (SWBNO): Manages water, sewage, and drainage services.
- **Permits and Licensing:**
 - City Permits and Licenses: Handles permits and licensing for various activities, including building permits, business licenses, and more.
- **Waste Management:**
 - Sanitation Services: Responsible for trash pickup and recycling programs.
- **Housing and Urban Development:**
 - New Orleans Department of Housing and Community Development: Manages housing and community development programs.
- **Emergency Preparedness:**
 - Office of Homeland Security and Emergency Preparedness (NOHSEP): Coordinates disaster preparedness and response efforts.
- **Animal Control and Welfare:**
 - Louisiana SPCA: Provides animal control and welfare services.
- **Senior Services:**
 - New Orleans Council on Aging: Offers services for senior citizens.

RANKING AND POSITIONING

New Orleans has been described as the "most unique" in the United States. The city perfectly merges modernity and culture in one place. A real taste of the past can be experienced when in New Orleans. It is distinct with its architectural character that combines multiple colonial traditions. The city boasts an atmosphere of a foreign city, with architectural adaptations and native ingenuity dating back to colonial times.

CREDIT RATINGS

Rating Agency	Rating	Outlook
Fitch	A	Stable
Standards & Poor	A+	Stable
Moody's	A2	Stable

FINANCIAL REPORT DECEMBER 2022

This section of the report focuses on the analysis of the financial report and the financial situation of the City of New Orleans for the year 2022. The objective of this report is to provide a comprehensive overview of the city's financial performance during this specific period, with an emphasis on the way the city manages financial resources.

The following financial information comes from the [2022 Annual Comprehensive Financial Report](#) available at city's web site.

The following statements conform to accounting principles, as set forth by the Governmental Accounting Standards Board, and have been audited by independent auditors in accordance with generally accepted auditing standards.

AUDIT REPORT

The auditors have examined governmental activities, component units, major funds, and remaining fund information of the city of New Orleans, Louisiana for the year ended December 31, 2022. and their opinion is that the financial statements present fairly the financial position of the City's various entities as of December 31, 2022, and the changes in financial position for the year ending on that date. This opinion is based on accounting principles generally accepted in the United States of America.

Auditor's objectives are to obtain reasonable assurance about whether the financial statements as a whole are free from material misstatement, whether due to fraud or error, and to issue an auditors' report that includes our opinion.

RESPONSIBILITIES OF MANAGEMENT

Management is responsible for the preparation and fair presentation of the financial statements in accordance with accounting principles generally accepted in the U.S., and for the design, implementation, and maintenance of internal control relevant to the preparation and fair presentation of financial statements that are free from material misstatement.

In preparing the financial statements, management is required to evaluate whether there are conditions or events, considered in the aggregate, that raise substantial doubt about the City's ability to continue as a going concern for twelve months beyond the financial statement date.

Source: Annual Comprehensive Financial Report 2022, City of New Orleans

Net Position

December 31, 2022 and 2021

(Amounts in thousands)

	Governmental Activities	
	2022	2021
Current and other assets	1,180,021	1,218,178
Capital assets	2,262,603	2,098,531
Total assets	3,442,624	3,316,709
Deferred amounts related to net pension liability	205,831	180,369
Deferred amounts related to OPEB	34,660	41,488
Deferred loss on bond refunding	2,760	3,229
Total deferred outflows	243,251	225,086
Long-term liabilities	2,413,158	2,616,875
Other liabilities	336,566	228,153
Total liabilities	2,749,724	2,845,028
Deferred amounts related to net pension liability	73,631	163,028
Deferred amounts related to OPEB	38,615	14,505
Deferred gain on bond refunding	376	478
Deferred amounts related to leases	6,654	-
Unavailable revenue	-	1,248
Total deferred inflows	119,276	179,259
Net position:		
Net investment in capital assets	1,203,318	1,409,432
Restricted	420,359	671,265
Unrestricted (deficit)	(806,803)	(1,563,189)
Total net position (deficit)	816,875	517,508

The City's net position on the government-wide basis was approximately \$816.87 million at December 31, 2022. The government-wide statement of activities reported an increase in net position of approximately \$299.4 million compared to the one of the year 2021.

STATEMENT OF ACTIVITIES COMPARISON

<u>Statement of Activities Comparison</u>		
Years Ended December 31, 2022 and 2021		
(Amounts in thousands)		
	<u>2022</u>	<u>2,021</u>
Revenues:		
Program revenues:		
Charges for services	310,360	242,053
Operating grants and contributions	321,544	312,844
Capital grants and contributions	150,276	208,986
General revenues:		
Property taxes	258,397	274,802
Sales taxes	273,023	218,860
Other taxes	67,401	52,447
Interest Revenue	15,962	7,871
Unrestricted investment income	5,354	5,764
Forgiveness of debt	-	-
Legal settlement	-	-
Property donation (note 6)	-	-
Miscellaneous	(715)	-
Loss on disposal of assets	-	-
Total revenues	<u>1,400,407</u>	<u>1,323,627</u>
Expenses:		
General government	418,858	363,892
Public safety	319,795	310,708
Public works	167,867	138,974
Health and human services	42,562	40,285
Culture and recreation	35,684	29,528
Urban development and housing	63,369	71,399
Economic development	10,039	12,198
Interest and fiscal changes	42,867	32,871
Total expenses	<u>1,101,040</u>	<u>999,855</u>
Change in net position	299,367	323,772
Net position beginning of year	517,508	193,736
Net position, ending	<u>816,875</u>	<u>517,508</u>

REVENUES

Total revenue increased by \$76.8 million or 5.8% from \$1.32 billion in 2021 to \$1.40 billion in 2022. This increase is primarily attributable to \$68 million of charges for services under general government; \$54 million of increased sales taxes remitted in the categories of general, motor vehicle, hotel/motel, and consumer, which are a direct result of the City of New Orleans tourism industry resurgence post COVID-19.

EXPENSES

Total expenses were \$1.101 billion in 2022, an increase of \$101.1 million, or 10.12%, compared to \$999.9 million in 2021. General government expense increased \$55.0 million, or 15.1%, from \$363.9 million in 2021 to \$418.9 million in 2022. Urban development and housing expense decreased \$8.0 million, or 11.25%, from \$71.4 million in 2021 to \$63.4 million in 2022. This increase is primarily due to an increase of grants received post COVID-19 and ARPA, which entitled the City of New Orleans to incur more expenses in 2022 than in 2021.

FUNDS

The report highlighted that, as of December 31, 2022, the City's governmental funds reported a combined fund balance of \$707.3 million.

At December 31, 2022, the general fund's fund balance increased by \$167.8 million from \$235.5 million in 2021, to 403.28 million in 2022.

Key factors relative to this change are:

- Expenditures increased in 2022 by \$48.66 million, which represents an 8.4% increase in expenditures
- Taxes revenues increased by \$62.21 million. The increase is due primarily to increased sales taxes remitted in the categories of general, motor vehicle, hotel/motel, and consumer, which are a direct result of the City of New Orleans tourism industry resurgence post COVID-19
- Charges for service revenues in the general fund increased by \$11.04 million in 2022 compared to 2021 primarily due to \$4.8 million in Sanitation Service Charges, \$3.7 million of Indirect Costs, and the remaining \$2.54 million from increased filming fees, parking meters, and property/sales tax collection fees
- Fines and fees revenues in the general fund increased by \$1.51 million in 2022 compared to 2021 primarily due to the decrease in traffic due to the COVID-19 pandemic which resulted in business and school closures and reduced enforcement of traffic laws.
- Miscellaneous revenues decreased by \$10.72 million compared to 2021 due to several factors including sundry, building and rents, insurance proceeds, and reimbursement for special activity.

In addition to the general fund, the report also discussed the FEMA Fund and the FTD Fund, highlighting their roles in managing grants related to disaster response and recovery, as well as funding related to the COVID-19 pandemic.

The FEMA Fund primarily accounts for grants received from the federal government as a result of Hurricanes Katrina, Rita, and Gustav.

Indeed, FEMA assists individuals as well as state and local governments with response to and recovery from disasters.

The FTD Fund primarily accounts for grants received from the federal government as a result of CARES (Coronavirus Aid, Relief, and Economic Security) 2020, Emergency Rental Assistance 2021, and ARPA (American Rescue Plan) 2021.

FTD assists individuals as well as state and local governments with response to and recovery from COVID-19.

Indeed, as the City of New Orleans moved forward into 2022, it faced various financial challenges, including reduced revenue streams due to the COVID-19 pandemic.

However, these funding programs contributed to the City's financial resilience.

As a result, the administration's goals for 2023 include post-pandemic recovery, expanding affordable housing, and a focus on a Violence Reduction Strategy through intergovernmental relations, communication, and community engagement.

OUTSTANDING DEBT

Outstanding Debt

	<u>2022</u>	<u>2021</u>
General obligation bonds	\$ 615,960	\$ 667,160
Taxable limited tax bonds	125,450	256,070
Limited tax bonds		
Revenue bonds and notes	70,690	81,475
Total bonds	<u>812,100</u>	<u>1,004,705</u>
Notes Payable (vehicle and equipment loans)	<u>2,666</u>	<u>3,198</u>
Go Zone Notes	<u>17,571</u>	<u>21,488</u>
Total outstanding debt	<u>\$ 832,337</u>	<u>\$ 1,029,391</u>

DISSEMINATION PLAN

Target

- Our citizen
- Business
- Investors
- Our employees

Purpose

Improve transparency, inform decision-making and building public trust by sharing a complete financial report and social overview of New Orleans

Channels

- City Website
- Press releases
- Social Media
- Public meetings

This report has been prepared by Alessia Riccumeni, Gaia Giorgi and Vittoria Macario Ban

Sources used:

- <https://nola.gov/next/home/>
- [New Orleans: Economy - Major Industries and Commercial Activity, Incentive Programs New and Existing Companies \(city-data.com\)](#)
- [New Orleans, LA | Data USA](#)
- [2023 New Orleans, LA Rankings - Niche](#)
- [New Orleans, Louisiana - WorldAtlas](#)
- [City of New Orleans Number of Employees, Statistics, Diversity, Demographics, and Facts - Zippia](#)
- <https://www.macrotrends.net/cities/23082/new-orleans/population>
- <https://www.census.gov/quickfacts/neworleanscitylouisiana>
- [2022 Annual Comprehensive Financial Report](#)

This work was completed as a part of the Public Management course at SAA, University of Turin, under the supervision of Prof. Valerio Brescia. The elements presented in the assignment have been developed in accordance with the guidelines defined by Professors Paolo Biancone, Silvana Secinaro, Valerio Brescia and Davide Calandra.